

China Regional Development

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"The Fourth Industrial Revolution is unfolding at an exponential rather than a linear pace."- China's President Xi Jinping

Actually the competitive world, with the apparently spontaneous initiatives of economic agents, is the key to understanding the new urban economy. Expressions like "vertical disintegration" and "social division of labour" are on the agenda for researchers. However, this contradiction between business subjectivity and social coherence must be regulated in some way. In this sense, the materialization of activities in space, before any other activity, even before the constitution of the market, is the first form of regulation.

Conceptual - Regional Development

Space and Region

The idea of n-dimensional abstract space is more appropriate to analyze a country's intricate economic interrelations. Objects would be defined by means of abstract relations, with as many spaces as there were systems of abstract relations that defined an object, or as many spaces as were the economic phenomena studied.

In this way, economic activities would no longer be "localized", with a distinction between geographic or ordinary space and economic spaces. The taxonomy of the economic space could then be done as follows:

- i) As the content of a plan;
- ii) As a force field;
- iii) As a homogeneous set .

Laws of Nature are the science of physical laws relating to the land.

The common space is where the company is located. But the company also occupies a place defined in another plan, understood as the set of the company's relations with its customers, suppliers, the State and competitors. Such a plan changes over time and cannot therefore be mapped.

The company is also subject to a force field, attracting and removing objects and activities. This determines the zone of economic influence that most often transcends the zone of topographic influence. Finally, the company occupies a space determined by a homogeneous group, with regard to its relations with other companies. In this

way, companies that had a common market of factors or final goods, even if they were at a great physical distance, would be in the same economic space.

In this way, the concept of growth pole is better understood through this abstract view of space, with polarization taking place in the economic matrix, and territorial concentration appearing only as a specificity of the phenomenon.

Boudeville's concept of economic space, is somewhat different. Boudeville does not consider the economic space to be abstract, but concrete, at the same time material and human. In the economic space conceived by Boudeville, in an input-output matrix, for example, economic variables and their interrelations could be represented, regardless of their geographic location. The economic space would be the Cartesian product of the matrices that represent the space of activities and the geographical space.

For Boudeville (1972, p.25), the big difference between the concept of space and that of region is in the fact that region is a continuous surface. "The region is opposed to space because it is composed of geographic elements that are necessarily continuous, of spatial elements that have common borders". In addition, it should be noted that the sum of the regions does not necessarily constitute an economic area.

The contiguity effect principle is, in itself, quite simple: taking units of the territory as a whole at random, those immediately contiguous (topological distance I), then those that are relatively close (distances II, III, .. ., n):

1. °) show very similarities (homogeneity);
2. °) have the strongest and most hierarchical exchange connections (polarization);
3. °) have a stronger ability to discover a collective aspiration and establish an action plan to meet their common objectives (BOUDEVILLE, 1972, p.25).

It follows, then, that the closer the two areas are physically, the greater the intensity of the determinants of homogeneity, polarization and joint action.

For Boudeville, the basic problem of spatial analysis is the problem of scale. He understands that both space and the region can be seen from three distinct and complementary angles:

- i) from a descriptive perspective, with an emphasis on the notion of homogeneity;
- ii) from a functional perspective, centred on the notion of polarization;
- iii) under the prism of decision making for economic policy, with emphasis on the notion of space or program region.

The pragmatic character given by Boudeville to spatial analysis, emphasizing the aspects that can be used in regional planning, allowed the growth of regional development modelling around the world.

A fundamental question that must be answered by anyone who wants to study and model economic development is how regions grow and develop economically.

A large schematic aggregation of these approaches can be made under the names: Theory of Circular Causation, Theory of the Export Base and Theory of Polarization.

First, it is necessary to characterize the difference between a regional development theory and a general development theory.

This difference basically rests on the fact that the regional theory of development emphasizes different variables, rather than introducing new elements, in relation to the general theory of development.

Thus, a first important differentiation concerns the flow of goods, labour and capital, which, for the regional economy, is free and therefore subject to all the consequences caused by a great mobility of the factors of production and goods, including, in the case of free transit of goods, competition from products from the more developed regions.

For national economies, there are protection mechanisms, exercised through the control of imports and exports, via tariffs, differential exchange rates, etc.

In addition, national economies can control the entry of immigrants, if there is a problem of employment, as well as the flight of capital to other countries, by controlling the foreign currency, while regional economies have to be subject to the single national currency.

A regional development theory must take into account the effect of this mobility on the development of the region. This factor can act in two ways:

- The development process can induce changes in the patterns of flows observed so far;
- Given the characteristic of open economies that the regions have, these can count, for their growth, in addition to their own resources, with those of other regions.

Another factor that must be taken into account in the regional economy is the fact that the spatial distribution of natural resources and consumer markets is not the same for all regions. In this sense, the theory of location has been a powerful aid to the regional economy, improving the understanding of these phenomena.

In summary, when introducing the regional element into a theory of economic development, it becomes necessary to include the following phenomena peculiar to the regional economy:

- The fact that resources are unevenly distributed across regions;
- Factor of mobility between regions, although far from perfect.

Once these elements were established as the main ones for the elaboration of a theory of regional economic development, it is necessary to gather other elements taken from the general economic theory, in order to establish a structure that allows us to analyze the varied theoretical approaches, which seek to answer the question initially placed.

Export Base Theory

This is a theory of regional development that considers export activities as the engine of that development. It was initially established to explain the development of Canadian and American regions in the 19th century. Although of recent origin, at least with this name and in the emphasis given to regional problems, its main idea is older.

Urban planners and geographers, when analyzing the urban economy, launched their first ideas about the concept of "base". They classified as basic the economic activities that sell their products beyond their borders, and, as non-basic, those that serve to support basic activities.

The source of growth for these economies depends on the development of basic activities, which makes it possible to import goods and services not produced locally and induces the growth of non-basic activities.

The attempt to extrapolate the theory of economic base in a theory of economic development of cities and even of regions was followed by several criticisms. It is necessary to establish that exports cannot be considered as the only source of variation in employment and income in a city.

Thus, variations in employment due to variations in the propensities to save and import, in non-local government spending in the city, and in payments to factors of production that live in other cities commonly occur.

More than that, autonomous investment, not considered by the export theory, since it cannot be explained by any functional relationship at the city level, can represent an important source of change in the urban network.

In addition to these, other factors, not always of an economic nature, such as population growth and technological progress, can influence the city's income.

However, the condition "ceteris paribus" ("all other things being equal.") is included in any attempt to project the relationship between localized employment and non-localized employment.

Thus, it is assumed that the only factor that causes variations in localized employment and total employment is variations in export activities, not localized. But, if other factors, such as those mentioned above, can also influence the level of employment, the analysis can only be done in the short term, since in the long term it cannot be guaranteed that they will not undergo changes.

Thus, the economic base has its application limited to the short term and is not able to explain, by itself, the long-term development or decline of cities or regions.

Another severe criticism of the theory of economic base as a technique for planning and as a theory for urban growth is that which does not recognize export activity as the engine for the development of cities and regions.

He proposes that non-basic or local activities should be seen as the real economic base, based on the fact that, as cities grow, the percentage of people employed in basic activities decreases. Even more, it is the capacity of local activities to support export activities that determines the possibility of developing cities.

In the model adopted until then, the structure of each region is taken into account according to the characteristics of the dominant export activity, which, in turn, was seen as dependent on the vicissitudes of the foreign market.

The proposal is to start examining the regions not only through the primary export model, but also to pay attention to the "potential for transformation" existing in each region.

Another very common criticism made to the theory of economic base is that it only examines the demand side, that is, given a variation in the demand for the region's product, it does not ask about the capacity that each region has in meeting that demand.

The theory of the economic base, therefore, would only examine the conditions necessary for demand, failing to examine sufficient conditions, supply. However, the attempt to extrapolate the economically based technique, to a theory of economic development of cities, comes up against the lack of theoretical content for such an undertaking.

In general, the beginning of the development process of a region is made through the export of some natural resource or some primary activity. This is particularly true for new regions - sparsely populated and without inhibiting traditions. Regions that do not

fit the above characteristics have less dependence on natural resources for their development.

Depressed regions also do not depend fundamentally on natural resources for their development, as they are characterized by having a developed industrial sector, although not very dynamic, low rates of economic growth and emigration of skilled workers. Its external and agglomeration savings are reasonable; the workforce and entrepreneurial capacity, however, are employed inefficiently. In these regions, the stimulus for development would come from a radical transformation of the industrial structure, adapting it to the reality of the national or international market.

Thus, the first step in analyzing the possibility for a region to meet external demand is to know the distribution of natural resources across regions, as well as their quality and intensity.

In addition, the region will have to place the export product on the market, at the price fixed by it. Under these conditions, the price will depend directly on the cost of production, which can be divided into transfer costs⁶ and processing costs.

The location of the region at this point is the most important factor.

Therefore, in the short term, the main determinants of the ability to meet external demand are the distribution of natural resources across the country, transfer costs and processing costs.

Finally, it is necessary that the region has some level of idle resources or a great mobility among its factors, in order, in the short term, to meet external demand.

Even if the region is able to meet external demand, this will not be enough to start a development process. For the development to occur, the conditions to be fulfilled are the maintenance of the dynamism of the product and the diffusion of this dynamism by other sectors of the economy.

Maintaining the dynamism of the export product is supported by the income elasticity of demand and the cost of the export product, as well as transaction costs. Ways to reduce costs are by improving the transport network and increasing factor productivity.

The spread of dynamism to other sectors in the region, in turn, is based on the characteristic of the export product that will determine the linkages and the diversity of the region's natural resources that will support the linkages.

Regions that have not yet experienced any significant development process, have low income, small population, at a time when the capitalist system prevails on the world

stage, which does not include regions underdeveloped countries, which, as a rule, have already undergone a significant development process.

The fundamental hypothesis of the export base theory is that it plays a vital role in determining the level of absolute and per capita income in a region. It should be noted, again, that North's theory refers to "young" regions, therefore without a complex and highly developed productive structure. Second, the importance of exports is crucial in shaping and conditioning the further development of a region. Thirdly, it is important to highlight the necessary, but not sufficient, nature of the export base for regional development, in the sense that it is necessary for the base to have an effect on other sectors, also developing them, and for income to be distributed reasonably among the population.

Production costs are of great importance in determining export capacity, but he considers that, although they are factors that will have some influence on the region's growth theory, they will not determine it. In addition, if the internal conditions of a region are considered to be the most relevant factors in the development process, it can be concluded that the more developed the region, the more it will develop which clarifies little about the causes of early development. Of course, in a short-term analysis, internal conditions can be preponderant.

Exports are a necessary but not a sufficient condition for regional development, and sufficiency involves the possibility of diversifying the base through other natural resources, the intensity of the chain effects and the pattern of income distribution caused by the base, and, finally, by improvements in productivity, costs and transportation.

The lack of detail on the issue of factor flows in open economies, the most characteristic element of the regional economy. Another neglected problem is the location of the base at a specific point within a region, because the regions cannot be considered completely homogeneous.

The fact that export-based models, as well as economic ones, are "demand models", insofar as they consider an exogenous variable, export, as strategic, and neglect endogenously determined internal factors, usually factors of the supply side.

The base models were methodologically inspired by the Keynesian multiplier, and, later, by the input-product matrix, which show what happens to an economy, with idle resources, if the final demand increases. In this line of reasoning, criticisms can be grouped, without losing sight of their interrelationship:

- a) supply factors are restrictions;
- b) the basic theory does not emphasize interregional links;

c) the study of regional supply curves as determinants of investment; d) the supply structure causes different impacts on the level of regional income.

In conclusion, it is possible to establish some fundamental points for understanding the theory of the export base:

i) Its difference in relation to the theory of the economic base is that it is more concerned with the analysis of the determination of income in the short term, Keynesian type, and the one with the long-term issue;

ii) It must be understood within the limits of its assumptions, not applying to any situation;

iii) It is not yet a complete and finished theory of regional development, as it does not sufficiently elaborate a crucial problem for the long-term development of the regions: the scarcity of factors and their interregional mobility;

iv) Does not pay attention to the supply side, excessively privileging the demand side.

It can also be argued that this theory provides many insights for those responsible for the elaboration of economic policies for the regions, such as the installation of industrial districts, the construction of large roads, the establishment of agricultural centres and the organization of growth poles.

Even so, the theory does not apply to underdeveloped countries, since the distribution of income in the export sector is usually in the hands of foreigners, given that the local sector does not react adequately to the profit opportunities created by the exporting sector and the nature of the good exported has a lower technological, processing degree.

The Circular Causation Theory

The second major schematic aggregation within regional analysis is the circular causation theory, which Myrdal (1968) had as its main formulator. He maintained that the principle of circular interdependence, within the process of cumulative causation, is valid throughout the field of social sciences and that this must be the main hypothesis to be considered in the study of underdevelopment and economic development.

His thought is that a simple circular causation model with cumulative effects is more typical of true social processes than the intersection of demand and supply curves at an equilibrium price, a symbol of reasoning in economic theory.

Following Myrdal's example, his proposal can be seen more clearly. So, consider the tax rate in a given community. Based on the assumption that local taxation may or may

not be levied directly on rents, it is established that as the income base compresses, the tax rate must be high.

The tax increase will encourage businesses and workers to leave the community, and will decrease the entry of businesses and workers from outside. Then, in a second phase, rents and demand will decrease again, and, consequently, will force the tax rate to rise further, having, again, effects similar to those already examined.

Likewise, the less favourable age distribution will not only have contributed to reducing the taxable per capita income, but also to increasing the relative need for public assistance services.

Evidently, if the income for the community does not come from raising taxes, some form of compensation should occur, such as cutting social expenses already programmed, with clear social consequences.

When, in states where the level of material well-being is high, the tax rate is prevented from rising, and yet public services maintain their standards, the explanation must be sought outside market forces, that is, national subsidies to the community and the establishment of minimum standards for public services.

These are the so-called compensatory changes, induced by organized society, which aim to restrict the blind law of cumulative social change, preventing it from promoting inequality.

The other side of the scale must also be shown. The cumulative process also works if the initial change is favourable.

Thus, the decision to locate an industry in a particular community, for example, boosts its overall development. The job possibilities and consequent income for those unemployed or underemployed workers would increase.

Local businesses would have new opportunities as demand for their products and services increased. Labour, capital and initiative are attracted from outside to take advantage of expansion opportunities. The establishment of a new business, or the expansion of an existing business, expands the market to other markets, as occurs, in general, with the increase in rents and demand.

Rising profits increase savings, while raising demand and profit levels once again. The expansion process creates external economies favourable to its continuity.

The local tax rate can be reduced, and the quantity and quality of public services improved. These changes will make the community more attractive to businesses and workers, with a greater contribution of financial resources, being naturally taken to the region.

Myrdal argued that the game of market forces tends, in general, to increase regional inequalities, not to reduce them. In his opinion, if there was no interventionist policy, market forces would determine that almost all economic activities - which in the developing economy tend to provide much higher than average earnings - as well as other activities, such as science, art, literature, education and higher culture, would be concentrated in certain regions, leaving the rest of the country somewhat stagnant.

Initially, purely geographical aspects would form the scene, with shopping centres concentrated in regions conducive to building a port, and industrial centres close to energy sources and inputs.

But, defends Myrdal, the current power of attraction of an economic centre originates mainly in a fortuitous historical fact, that is to say, that a movement started, with success, and not in several other places, where it could, likewise, having started with equal or greater success.

Thereafter, the ever-growing internal and external economies have strengthened and maintained their continued growth at the expense of other locations and regions, where, on the contrary, stagnation or relative regression has become the norm.

If we classify migration, capital movement and trade as means by which the cumulative process develops, we will see that they can have positive effects in certain regions and negative effects in others.

The locations and regions where economic activity is expanding will attract mass immigration from other parts of the country, and, since migration is selective, at least with respect to the age factor, this movement will tend to favour fast-growing communities and harm others. In addition, the poorest regions will also have a relatively higher birth rate, which will aggravate the age problem in the working population of those regions.

Capital movements tend to have similar effects on the growth of inequalities. In expansion centres, the increase in demand will give an impetus to investment, which, in turn, will increase rents and demand, causing a second flow of investments, and so on.

Savings will increase as a result of higher rents, but will tend to be lower than investment, in the sense that the capital supply would have to satisfy an active demand. In the other regions, the lack of a new expansionist impulse means that the demand for capital remains weak even compared to savings, which will be small, because incomes are also and tend to decline.

Studies carried out in many countries reveal how the banking system, when not controlled to operate differently, tends to become an instrument that drains savings

from the poorest to the richest and most progressive regions, where the return on capital is high and safe.

In the operation of trade, the same fundamental preference is noted in favour of the more affluent and progressive regions, to the detriment of others.

The improvement of national markets will help to discourage the first industrial diversification initiatives in agricultural regions.

The cumulative processes that tend to regional inequality operate through many causal chains, which, as a rule, are not considered in the theoretical analysis of market forces.

Part of these chains are selectivity in migration, the effects of poverty on birth and the competitive disadvantages of non-expansionist regions. All the inhibitory effects of misery, operating by means other than those analyzed by traditional economic theory, non-economic factors, therefore, are interdependent in circular causation with each other and all with the preferences indicated in the case of migrations, capital movements and trade.

Still in Myrdal's formulation, economic theory has not considered so-called non-economic factors and keeps us out of the scope of analysis. Such factors appearing among the main vehicles, according to him, in the circular cause of the cumulative processes of economic change, its omission represents one of the main deficiencies of economic theory.

In opposition to the "regressive effects" there are certain centrifugal "propelling effects", which spread from the centre of economic expansion to other regions.

They are linked to the cumulative social process by circular causation, as are "regressive effects", as opposed to which they have created compensatory changes.

They represent a complication of the main hypothesis, according to which, normally, changes in other factors, which are born as reactions arising from the change of one factor, always tend to set the system in motion, towards the initial change.

However, under no circumstances do "propelling effects" make it possible to establish the assumptions for an equilibrium analysis. In the marginal case, the two kinds of effects will compensate each other and a region will be in stagnation.

But this position is not in a stable equilibrium, because any change in the opposing forces will trigger a cumulative upward or downward movement.

Myrdal stresses that the realistic study of any process will have to consider a wide variety of interrelated changes differently, in response to primary changes, and does

not deny that these changes are often interrelated in such a way that they compensate each other.

However, when the main trends over more or less long periods are considered, the changes will strengthen each other and will therefore tend to have cumulative net effects.

He suggests that the problem of the "business cycle", that is, changes in general economic conditions, undergo a deeper investigation of these changes, which would include research into the differences between localities and regions, as these differences change under the influence of the game of market forces.

The Polarization Theory

The third major schematic theoretical aggregation that addresses the problem of how regions grow and develop is called polarization theory. This emerged in France, after the Second World War, in the context of a world capitalist system increasingly dominated by the United States, and in the middle of a process of independence and reunification, with regard to the colonies, which successively receive their "political autonomy" .

The theory was developed by F. Perroux (1967) and, according to him, a development pole would be an aggregation of propelling industries, generating diffusion effects in a larger region, it is not possible to know which are the propelling industries due to their rate of relative expansion.

A development pole may have a lower growth rate than that of cities, whose expansion depends basically on the investments initially made in the pole.

Perroux begins his work by analyzing models in balanced growth, which are logical instruments to highlight and classify changes, if we consider that the economy, in reality, does not behave in a balanced way.

It starts by considering that the quantities in the economy, or the economic factors, are only multiplied by a constant, without changing the proportions between flows. Then, it analyzes that the quantities in the economy rise in the same proportion, from period to period, and the flows increase without changes in structures.

The answer to the basic question that Perroux asks, why the economy changes, is that this is due to the appearance and disappearance of industries, and, also, to the different growth rates among the most varied industrial sectors throughout the same period or successive periods.

What Perroux (1967) tries to answer next is where this occurs:

The rude, but true, fact is this: growth does not appear simultaneously everywhere. On the contrary, it manifests itself in growth poles, with varying intensities, expands through several channels and with different final effects on the entire economy.

The study was then divided into blocks, covering the driving industry and growth, the industry complex and growth, and the expansion of growth poles and the growth of national economies.

The driving industry takes the form of a "modern industry", with above-average growth rates for specific periods, acting on other industries and on the overall product of the economy.

When acting on other industries, as individualized firms, considering perfect competition, it acts on interdependence for the single price; already as external economies, it creates a link based on the technique used and its changes and not just on price.

These relations between firms and industries can be extended and the immediate external economy will be applied, leading to an understanding of growth:

- i) Expansion (short term) and growth (long term) of large groups of firms;
- ii) Difference between investment decided by a single company according to profitability, and investment decided taking into account benefits and induced profits.

When acting on the global product of the economy, the birth of a new industry is always the result of an expectation. One or more agents propose to face a new situation and assume the risks of its realization. Once these plans are compatible with the plans of other agents, in the same set, the expectation becomes creative.

Then, three situations can happen:

- a) If the factors employed are idle and the creation does not cause damage to any other sector, the new industry will raise the overall product of the economy;
- b) If the factors used are "substitution", the overall product still has a net gain;
- c) If part of the factors is removed from the previous circuits, the net increase will be the algebraic sum of the losses and gains in productivity. A

After joining the economy, one can analyze its participation, first in the global product, and secondly in the product supplement, from period to period, which it induces in its environment, because in addition to not appearing in isolation it adds its own product and induced from the new industries taken together.

Innovation implies destabilizing the economy, creating inequalities between agents, intensifying the desire for relative gains and power. In this way, it is admitted that there is no real situation that expresses the stationary equilibrium, and this is an instrument to register changes in the system, from competition to monopoly, thus opening up the concept of industry complex. This does not consist of a group of industries, simply, but of a key industry, a non-competitive regime and a territorial agglomeration.

Key industry is that which has the property to increase the sale of others, with the aim of making better use of its installed fixed capital and reducing its cost up to the optimum point. Increasing your sales can boost sales for related industries. This can occur to varying degrees, and it is called a key industry to that which induces a total global increase in excess of its own sales.

The industrial complex regime is, in itself, destabilizing, as it is an oligopolistic combination, and its consequence is a growth spurt when, in the long run, capital accumulation is higher than it would be if the industry were subjected to a regime of greater competition and that causes, at the same time, the expansion and growth of related industries.

Even so, this industrial regime does not demonstrate the instability resulting from each industry being a supplier and customer of the others, even subject to the influence of public authorities.

Territorial agglomeration adds specific characteristics to the above elements, intensifies economic activities, raises consumers with different and progressive patterns, links collective needs and determines that producers influence each other. The complex industrial pole changes the geographic environment and, if it is powerful, changes the structure of the national economy, creating new centres of accumulation.

The growth of the market resulting from the communication of industrial centres is contrary to the growth equally distributed, operating by irradiation, and thus altering the growth of national economies and their development.

When analyzing the growth poles, relating them to national economies, it can be said that the territory is no longer just a place where a population lives, but rather a combination of additive sets, represented by driving industries, industrial poles and agglomerated activities, with relatively passive groups represented by related industries and regions dependent on the poles, where the former transmit growth to others with its consequences.

Thus, in the first place, a conflict of non-coincidence between economic and political spaces is created.

Large economic units are instruments of prosperity and weapons of the national state, resulting in a combination of private and public powers in the management of these units, in a struggle between capitalists and nationalists on a global level.

Second, as long as national and nationalist policies persist in a world overtaken by technology, obstacles to growth will persist, even without violent conflicts.

Each State strives to exploit the poles it owns for the exclusive benefit of its citizens, and uses part of its resources to exclude its competitors from the advantages of the exclusivity of these poles.

Hence the struggle between quasi-public oligopolies that endanger prosperity and peace.

The elimination or reduction of these practices is an important policy of balanced growth on a worldwide scale.

Interpretation of Regional Development

The interpretation of regional economic development is at an intermediate point between the tendency towards normalization, present in most works on the theme, and the necessary specificity for the analysis to be coherent.

The planning of regional economic development can be divided in terms of economic organization, development styles and the prevailing concepts of economic development (BOISIER, 1980).

The public and private sectors must have a recognized role in regional development and can, without distinction, generate public policies, that is, take decisions that affect macroeconomic parameters and variables.

The most important consequence of the system being mixed or hybrid capitalist is the need to consider the logic of the expansion and reproduction of the system in spatial terms.

Developing countries usually have an economic organization corresponding to mixed capitalist systems, with different modalities of insertion in the international economy, with more or less significant areas of social, state in most cases, and community property in some (BOISIER, 1980).

The notion of development style, according to Boisier, is a parameter to be considered in any interpretation of regional development that intends to go beyond the abstractionism of the theories in force in this matter.

Each of these elements gives rise to three subtypes:

a) Predominant Resource Allocation Mechanism is subdivided into Market with subsidiary State, Market partially corrected and Regulated market;

b) Social and Welfare Policies are subdivided into subsidiary social policy, complementary social policy and direct pursuit of social objectives;

c) Treatment of Foreign Capital and External Opening are divided into Wider Opening, Regulated Opening and Restricted Opening. Automaticity or discretion is what will differentiate one economic policy process from another.

Industrialization as the engine of the general process of development and social modernization, more than the processing of natural resources, seems to be an element of the set of basic characteristics of the dominant regional paradigm which is, in turn, a partial expression of the global style (BOISIER, 1980).

As a logical consequence, regional industrialization policies were a priority in national development plans and brought, linked to them, the second characteristic of the dominant paradigm, namely, urbanization.

The difficulty of avoiding the lack of synchrony between the patterns of industrialization and urbanization caused situations of premature urbanization and hyperurbanization, which ended up stimulating and feeding back urban industrialization as a way of reducing occupational problems.

The third characteristic of the dominant paradigm is the centralization in decision-making processes.

This is a phenomenon resulting from a very complex picture of factors, in which historical, cultural, technological and ideological elements are mixed.

Geographical, Population and Administrative Aspects of the People's Republic of China

The People's Republic of China covers an area of 9,596,961 km², is the third largest country in the world, lagging behind Russia and Canada.

From this territory, with immense mineral reserves, almost half present inhospitable conditions for occupation - this is the Gobi desert area and the northwest area under

influence of Tibet, whose geography is dominated by the Himalayas and its ramifications. Its climate is marked by the monsoons of the Southeast, which that winters are dry and summers are damp.

Compared to other nations in large territories, such as India, the United States and Russia, the country has the smallest arable area per capita and, considering the low endowment of forests and water, it is understood why, in an era high industrialization and urbanization, the question of the environment assumes dramatic characteristics and can effectively operate as a limiter of the endogenous development.

At the end of 2014, the Chinese population totalled 1,367,820,000 people, confirming the status of the most populous country in the world.

The urban population resident was 749.16 million (54.77%) and rural, 618.66 million (45.23%).

The number of men surpassed the number of women, 51.2% and 48.8%, respectively. The demographic pyramid shows that the population between 15 and 59 represents 67% of the total. Adding the population above 60 years, it reaches the 82.5% mark. The population between 0 and 15 years old represented 17.5%.

This profile population growth was achieved very quickly and is partly a consequence of the past one-child policy and advancing longevity.

The country is divided into 31 provinces, representing federative units; many of them are long-lived, and a few are of more recent creation.

In fact, they can be further subdivided into four municipalities under supervision national, five autonomous regions of ethnic minorities and 22 provinces.

Accelerated urbanization has produced a city scene marked by high population concentration, with four or five megacities (as adopted methodology) above 10 million inhabitants and more than 14 cities with inhabitants above 5 million. Beijing and Shanghai are the two largest metropolises, around 20 million inhabitants, each, and an impressive polarizing power that extends to Tianjin, in the case of the first, and throughout the Yangtze Delta, in the case of the second.

The population is concentrated more to the East, and most of the main economic activities, in the regions of the two large hydro graphic basins in the Yang Tse and Yellow rivers.

Although strongly centralized, the governmental structure ensures a relevant role in making investments to local entities, as long as they are inserted in the guidelines and commands of the central government.

Despite being studied as a federation, in many aspects, the sovereignties of provincial and municipal entities are totally subordinate to the command of the single party, without, however, eliminating the games of regional interest, among the various entities with degrees of manoeuvre reasonably high, much more similar to a country of unitary organization than that of a federative organization.

Nor is the existence of autonomous regions sufficient to define a federative organization, which does not prevent, in order to analyze regional development and the role of local governments, a flexible federative approach is appropriate.

Two aspects of Chinese development stand out. First, the complexity of the strategy, given the capacity to compose the path of development, for practically all possible sectorial policies, in a complementary and coordinated way.

Everything needed to happen at the same time: on the external and on the domestic scene, involving macroeconomic policies, industrial policies, financial and credit policies.

The design and management of this set of interventions they belonged to the party, as well as the centralized planning system and a sophisticated technical area trained at universities in China, the United States and Europe.

Second, the permanence of the options followed throughout the time and, within these parameters originally defined in the late 1970s, the production of adjustments and adaptation to the questions that are being asked material advancement.

This feature of Chinese development (perhaps ancestral) is linked to the party and the specificities of the political regime. Note that accelerated growth did not necessarily mean "wild capitalism" because, like it or not, the strong control exercised over the population prevented their free movement and the formation of slums. This did not prevent the production of new urban poor useful to globalized manufactures.

It does not seem right to pursue two frequent qualifications given to Chinese development: one that claims that there was a collapse of socialism and that elites bowed to capitalism, and another that referred to capitalism of authoritarian techno bureaucratic state as an expression of the Chinese model, nullifying the historical role of socialism.

In this sense, it is recommended, until proven otherwise, to follow the government nomenclature which claims to be a model of market socialism with Chinese characteristics.

Its socialist base refers to the State and the dimension of its dominion over productive, financial capital, over land and population. Nomenclatures aside, foreign capital does not seem to have been frightened by the state's supremacy in the giant's trajectory.

The Policies of development

Deng Xiaoping made it very clear why the new paths: there was no way to sustain a regime that could not consistently raise the standard of living of the people, trapped in economic backwardness.

Following a persistent gradualist line, through reforms and prudent opening, using special zones as platforms for experimentation (with emphasis, in the first place, on the various forms of association with foreign capital and the mechanisms of technology transfer), the transformations they occurred in an accelerated and sustained manner by the State's economic command.

Society has also changed, raising new questions and problems whose solutions may prove to be decisive for the survival of the socialist regime, at an unprecedented level or at a higher stage (according to Chinese leaders the stage of primary socialism - which prioritizes the development of productive forces - would be exhausted by the 2050s).

The Chinese trajectory, at least since 1949, revives the old debate about reform or revolution. During the Cultural Revolution, Mao, in a radical and simplistic way, tried to impose an egalitarian ethic, without wealth, paradoxically close to the Buddhist lifestyle.

Deng Xiaoping proposed, to produce a profound structural change, gradualism and the path of reforms. But, in a historical evaluation, reformism produced revolutionary changes that accelerated historical time due to the intense industrialization and urbanization generated.

Despite being a member of the BRICS, a group of developing countries called emerging, China reaches, with its GDP, the second place among all countries on the planet. From an economic perspective, it maintains centre-periphery relations with all developing countries, some developed (e.g. Australia), in addition to the other members of the BRICS; that is, it exports industrialized products and imports agricultural and industrial commodities.

If China manages to resolve the impasses between sustaining an industry manufacturing, low wages, with good results abroad and, on the other hand, the transition to an industrial structure dominated endogenously by high technology, there are good chances that, for many countries, this means deindustrialization perhaps definitive.

The size of the Chinese population and the rapid change in its demographic pyramid make this nation a unique case, with scales difficult to be understood by analysts.

Behind this change are economic and social changes; but, also, an important part of this complex dynamic is the result of regulatory policies on the behaviour of the population, with emphasis on the one-child rule and the hukou system.

Today fears are growing about the negative impact of the rapid aging of individuals on the labour market, with a reduction in the active population in 2014 of -3.7%.

The government is gradually loosening the one-child policy, but families, as in developed countries, they show little propensity to have more children, due to lack of time or economic insecurity, so that until now demographic change seems irreversible.

In turn, migratory flows towards cities (in numbers unprecedented in the history of mankind) did not result in the formation of urban clusters that lack basic services and public policies, although they were decisive in sustaining the low wage standard.

The pattern of urbanization that followed industrialization in China was also highly concentrated, making populous megacities a centre of national and regional economic power, giving little space for development autonomous from medium-sized cities.

With the capitalist transformations underway, in unprecedented levels of concentration and centralization of capital, in a socialist formation under the command of the Communist Party, there was an increase in the levels of inequality, between wages and profits, within the wage structure and between the rural environment and the urban environment (although that distance is narrowing).

Parts of the challenges that arise are related to the task of reducing social distances and ensuring the conditions for social peace and the longevity of the system.

His apparent lack of interest in disputing political and military hegemonies that already existed in Western capitalism is probably a precaution and a trick for economic relations to continue to evolve despite profound political differences - see the distance with Cuba.

The billionaire projects for the new sea and land silk routes (in alliance with Russia) are considered a response to the American stance in the Pacific area. However, its relations with Russia, since Mao's time, have had ups and downs. One of the reasons for the shift towards the United States in the second half of the 1970s was the belief that the then Soviet Union was about to invade Chinese territory.

There are serious political issues with Tibet. This autonomous region, together with the surrounding Xinjiang province, showed growth rates above 10% indicating a strategy to increase investments in infrastructure and the presence of the State through the economic route, to weaken regional autonomous impulses.

The transition in the economic field translates into the implantation and diffusion of an endogenous growth-inducing matrix, marked by innovation and high technology. In a scenario gloomy world, it is a response to the exhaustion of a certain type of industry, both with regard to its international insertion and its capacity to provide internal responses in line with the impressive demographic changes with premature population aging.

Conclusion

We analysed Regional Development in the base of Space and Region. We concluded that economic agents, is the key to understanding the new urban economy with "vertical disintegration" and "social division of labour".

We found different theories on Regional Development:

- 1 - Export Base Theory;
- 2 - The Circular Causation Theory and
- 3 - The Polarization Theory.

In China we can find a deep regional inequality that inverted-U theory tends to rise during the early stages of development and to fall as the economy matures.

However China regional development continues to be constrained by the obligation to justify official policy, and a lack of attention to firms, enterprises, and the relations between production and space.

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